

2015 FSL Course Hawaii, USA

Timetable

	Monday 8 June	Tuesday 9 June	Wednesday 10 June	Thursday 11 June	Friday 12 June
8:00	Course Registration				
8:30-10:00 main lectures	Intro to Imaging, Overview of FSL, Brain-extraction (BET) <i>MJ</i>	Diffusion MRI Analysis (FDT/TBSS) <i>SS/JA</i>	FMRI 1 - Preprocessing & Simple Stats (FEAT) <i>MJ</i>	FMRI 3 - Advanced FMRI Analysis (FEAT) <i>CB/JB</i>	ICA - Exploratory FMRI Analysis (MELODIC) <i>CB</i>
10:00-10:30	Tea & Coffee				
10:30-12:00	Practical session				
12:00-1:30	Lunch				
1:30-3:00 main lectures	Registration & Unwarping (FLIRT, FNIRT & FUGUE) <i>MJ</i>	Diffusion Tractography (FDT) <i>MB</i>	FMRI 2 - Permutation Testing & Multi-Subject Stats (Randomise & FEAT) <i>MJ</i>	Structural Segmentation (FAST, FIRST, SIENA, FSL-VBM) <i>MJ</i>	Resting-State and Connectivity Analysis (dual regression) <i>CB/JB</i>
3:00-3:30	Tea & Coffee				
3:30-5:00	Practical session				
5:00-6:00 evening lectures	Intro to MRI acquisition <i>KM</i>	Intro to FMRI acquisition <i>KM</i>	Applications in Clinical Research <i>TBC</i>	Human Connectome Project <i>DVE</i>	FSL Future Work <i>MJ</i>
6:00-8:30	Evening reception				

FSL Course

Basic Anatomy

Basic Anatomy

The brain is full of neurons. These are organised into two types of “tissues”:

- Grey Matter
- White Matter

White Matter

MRI

Neurons

Basic Anatomy

Neurons are densely connected and have *many* dendrites

Basic Anatomy

Neurons are densely connected and have *many* dendrites

Axons conduct electrical signals and are surrounded by myelin

Myelin is a major factor
in determining the MR
signal and contrast

FSL Course

Applications of MRI in neuroimaging

Neuroimaging research examples: neuroscience

**Structural
MRI**

**Functional
MRI (task)**

**Diffusion
MRI**

**Functional
MRI
(resting)**

Neuroimaging research examples: neuroscience

- Study of taxi drivers showing structural plasticity

**Structural
MRI**

Maguire et al.,
PNAS, 2000

Neuroimaging research examples: schizophrenia

Diffusion
MRI

- White matter integrity - imaging tissue nature change
- Damage to brain connectivity - reduction in schizophrenia in corpus callosum, fornix, longitudinal fasciculus

Neuroimaging research examples: stroke therapy

**Single
subject:
responder**

Unaff.
hand
(right)

Pre 1

Pre 2

Aff.
hand
(left)

THERAPY

Post 1

Post 2

**Group:
Correlations
with
improvement**

**Functional
MRI (task)**

Johansen-Berg, et al.,
Brain 2002

Neuroimaging research examples:

Altered functional connectivity in young, healthy carriers of APOE-ε4

Distinct patterns of brain activity in young carriers of the APOE-ε4 allele

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Edited by Robert W. Mahley, The J. David Gladstone Institutes, San Francisco, CA, and approved March 6, 2009 (received for review November 25, 2008)

The APOE ε4 allele is a risk factor for late-life pathological changes that is also associated with anatomical and functional brain changes in middle-aged and elderly healthy subjects. We investigated structural and functional effects of the APOE polymorphism in 18 young healthy APOE ε4-carriers and 18 matched noncarriers (age range: 20–35 years). Brain activity was studied both at rest and during an encoding memory paradigm using blood oxygen level-dependent fMRI. Resting fMRI revealed increased “default mode network” (involving retrosplenial, medial temporal, and medial-prefrontal cortical areas) coactivation in ε4-carriers relative to noncarriers. The encoding task produced greater hippocampal activation in ε4-carriers relative to noncarriers. Neither result could be explained by differences in memory performance, brain morphology, or resting cerebral blood flow. The APOE ε4 allele modulates brain function decades before any clinical or neurophysiological expression of neurodegenerative processes.

hippocampus | memory | neuroimaging | resting connectivity

fMRI studies have tested for early life associations of the APOE polymorphism with changes in brain function. Filbey et al. (18) reported greater activation in 8 APOE ε4-carriers compared with 8 noncarriers in medial frontal and anterior cingulate areas using a working memory task. In contrast, we observed reduced activation in ε4-carriers relative to noncarriers in the same areas. Both studies used resting fMRI to investigate intrinsic brain networks. Here, we used structural and functional MRI to investigate the effects of APOE ε4-carriers relative to noncarriers in young healthy subjects (20 to 35 years). We found that ε4-carriers showed greater spontaneous fluctuations in brain activity relative to noncarriers, particularly in the default mode network, showing a pattern of increased activity in the default mode network frequency fluctuations (less than 0.1 Hz) are defined as “resting state networks” (RSNs), and they reflect intrinsic properties of functional brain organization (21). We were specifically inter-

Functional
MRI
(resting)

Neuroimaging research examples:

Surgical planning

Diffusion
MRI

+

Functional
MRI (task)

(Bartsch et al., JMRI 2006)

Neuroimaging research examples: Parkinson's Disease

**Structural
MRI**

**Diffusion
MRI**

Look at tracts
~~connected to regions~~
of structural change

Right hemisphere:

Menke et al., Brain 2013

FSL Course

Introduction to MRI acquisition and analysis

MRI Analysis

- MRI is:

- noisy

- variable/configurable

- Analysis is:

- based on statistics _____

- has many options/alternatives _____

- has more than one “right” way (but many wrong)

- This course aims to:

- explain aspects needed to make good choices in the analysis, acquire good images, interpret the results

- present information relevant to using the methods, but not cover all the details of the inner workings

Overview

- Structural MRI
 - Diffusion MRI
 - Functional MRI
 - Complementary techniques
- } →
- Variety of acquisitions
 - Measurement basics
 - Limitations & artefacts
 - Analysis principles
 - Acquisition tips

Structural MRI

T₁-weighted

T₂-weighted

Proton
Density

- Images gross brain anatomy
- Time depends on SNR & resolution (typ. 5-15 mins)
- Many different (and good) varieties of sequences to acquire these images

Analysis of Structural MRI

- Quantify tissue volumes and structure shape/size

Tissue types: GM
/ WM / CSF

Sub-cortical
structure &
shape

Cortical
surfaces &
thickness

Local GM
changes

Structural MRI Measurement

- 3 main quantities involved here:
 - Density of water & fat (proton density)
 - T₁ relaxation time
 - T₂ relaxation time

Structural MRI Measurement

- 3 main quantities involved here:
 - Density of **water** & fat (proton density)
 - T_1 relaxation time
 - T_2 relaxation time
- Relaxation times depend on *many* things (e.g. molecular tumbling speed) but are sensitive to micro-environment and hence “tissue type”
- Intensity is usually a complicated weighting of different factors

Structural MRI “Limitations”

- Does *not* measure tissue type (GM/WM/CSF) directly
- It is not quantitative
- T₁ and T₂ values vary within GM and WM
(but this can be interesting!)
- Partial volume average of signals
- Does not distinguish bone from air
- Contrast can be poor/variable in subcortical regions
- Single sequence does not show all pathologies
- Artefacts and noise

Structural MRI Artefacts

Hardware-related

Contrast & Noise
(SNR & CNR)

Resolution & Partial Voluming

Low-res T₂-weighted

- There is always a trade-off in MRI between acquisition time, resolution and noise (Signal to Noise Ratio = SNR)
- For analysis it is Contrast to Noise Ratio (CNR) that is often more important, and contrast depends on MR sequence too

Structural MRI Artefacts

Hardware-related

RF Bias (B_1 inhomogeneity)

- Non-uniform RF field causes smooth variations in intensity
- Can sometimes be very large
 - less smooth for higher field (e.g. 7T) & multi-coil arrays
- Need to compensate in analysis

Structural MRI Artefacts

Physiological

Motion

can be problematic
- minimise at acquisition

Hardware/settings

Ghosting

normally very minor

Wrap-around

should always
be avoided

Structural MRI Artefacts

Hardware-related

RF Interference

RF Spiking

+ others... e.g. chemical shift (fat-water misaligned)

Most are serious but uncommon (easy to spot)

Structural MRI: Analysis

Basic stages in the structural analysis pipeline:

Brain Extraction

Segmentation
(tissue-type)

Segmentation
(structure)

Registration
(alignment)

Structural MRI: Analysis

Later stages in the structural analysis pipeline:

Statistics!
(often non-parametric)

Needed to investigate group-level changes/relations

Local GM changes

Local shape changes

Local thickness changes

Structural MRI: Acquisition

Basic tips for acquisition

- T_1 -weighted images tend to be the best for the SNR/time/resolution tradeoff (1mm voxels are typical)
- Use the locally optimised sequence on your scanner
 - there are many sequences names/types that give T_1 -weighted images and most are equally good
- If subjects are likely to move a lot then (offline) averaging several shorter acquisitions can be better
- Sub-cortical contrast can be enhanced with different sequences or parameter choices
- Turn on some fat-suppression (helps brain extraction)
- Isotropic voxels are *much* better for analysis in general
- Do not do upsampling on scanner (sometimes the default)

Structural MRI (2)

FLAIR

WM nulled

Double Inversion
Recovery (DIR)

- By changing timing and signals (RF/gradients) of MR sequence can *null* certain “tissues” or flows
- Useful for highlighting lesions/pathologies
- Also can give better sub-cortical contrast
 - e.g. Brainstem; Globus Pallidus internal/external

Structural MRI (2)

Analysis of pathological subjects

- Action required depends on:
 - type of analysis
 - type of pathology
- For obvious/severe pathology (e.g. lesion/tumour/stroke) then often need to manually create a mask
 - use mask in registrations and segmentations
 - can also apply this strategy to localised artefacts
- For subtle/small pathologies (e.g. diffuse hyper-intensities) can ignore it, depending on image quality (CNR, artefacts, etc.)

Structural MRI (3)

SWI / QSI

MT

Veno/Angio-grams

- By sensitising the sequence to different properties can detect other features of tissue:
 - SWI/QSI: S=susceptibility; magnetic field changes due to iron content (primarily) and myelin/WWM
 - MT: Magnetisation Transfer; bound/free water
 - Veno/Angio-grams: flow/blood iron/contrast agent

Structural MRI

Many other types of structural MRI, for example...

- | | |
|---|----------------------------------|
| • Susceptibility-Weighted Imaging (SWI) | <u>Sensitive to:</u>
iron |
| • Quantitative Susceptibility Imaging (QSI) | (and myelin) |
| • Magnetization Transfer (MT) | chemical species/
environment |
| • MR Spectroscopy (MRS) | |
| • Angiograms & Venograms | arteries & veins |
| • Quantitative T_1 and T_2 maps (relaxometry) | tissue μ structure |
| • Myelin maps | myelin |
| • B_0 map (fieldmap) | fields |
| • B_1 map (RF) | within head |

Diffusion MRI

- Measures microstructure directionality and “integrity”, particularly in WM
- Provides information on anatomical connectivity
- Need to acquire many “directions”: 5-30 min scan

Analysis of Diffusion MRI

local directions

Surrogate measures of *microstructure*
Local WM structure via tensor: directions, Mean Diffusivity (MD) and Fractional Anisotropy (FA) -

colour coded direction

Analysis of Diffusion MRI

Probabilistic Tractography

Tractography traces connections via local directions

Analysis of Diffusion MRI

Probabilistic Tractography can be used for connectivity-driven segmentation

Segmented seed region (thalamus)
- based on highest target probability

Target masks

Diffusion MRI Measurement

- Based on movement (diffusion) of water
- Restricted more in some directions than others - gives most information about axon directions in WM
- Gives information about *microstructure*, but *averaged over whole voxel*
- Sensitive to one direction per image;
 - ▶ lots of directions = lots of images
- Use FAST imaging (EPI) to get enough images

Mini MR Physics

Diffusion sensitizing (encoding) gradient

Gradient coils:
create magnetic
field changes in
any direction

Moving spins in the gradient direction change
“*phase*” and reduce in coherence (less signal)

Mini MR Physics

Diffusion sensitizing (encoding) gradient

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Diffusion MRI “Limitations”

- Does not measure axon size/density directly
- Does not measure single fibres (only average groups)
 - Difficult to deal with crossing/kissing fibres
- Quantitative local measurements, but not connectivity
- More difficult to do in pulsatile regions (e.g. brainstem)
- More restricted by hardware and SNR
- Sensitive to fast imaging artefacts

Diffusion MRI Artefacts

Hardware-related

Distortion

Eddy Currents

+ Bulk/Pulsatile Motion ... plus all the structural artefacts

- Eddy currents: both acquisition and analysis fixes needed
- Distortion due to B_0 inhomogeneity (air in sinuses)
 - acquisition-and-analysis related fixes needed
- Bulk motion is corrected for in acquisition (navigators)
- Pulsatile motion is more problematic

Diffusion MRI: Analysis

Basic stages in the diffusion analysis pipeline:

Eddy Current & Motion Correction

Fibre/
direction
modelling

“Tensor”
Fitting
e.g. FA, MD

Probabilistic Tractography

Diffusion MRI: Analysis

Later stages in the diffusion analysis pipeline:

Statistics
(non-parametric)

To investigate group-level changes/relations

FA changes in WM tracts

Tractography-based Segmentation

Diffusion MRI: Acquisition

Basic tips for acquisition

- Best parameters can be quite hardware dependent (esp. gradients) so check what is optimised for your scanner
- In general, b-value of 1000-1500 s/mm² and 60+ directions (tractography) or 12+ directions (FA, etc.) tend to give good results (but the more directions the better)
- Get one b=0 image for every 8-10 diffusion-weighted images
- Get even distribution of directions on a full sphere
- Choose a sequence that compensates for eddy currents (e.g. twice refocussed sequence, modified S-T, etc.)
- Get a fieldmap (B₀) for distortion correction - or alternatively, a blip-up-blip-down sequence (FSL tool - topup - out now!)
- Isotropic voxels (or close) are better for analysis generally
- *Do not* do upsampling on scanner (sometimes the default)
- Both single/multi-shell give good tractography

Functional MRI

- Measures haemodynamic response to neural activity
- Task-based or resting-state-connectivity
- Intrinsic contrast (BOLD) or explicit tag (ASL)
- Take many fast images (EPI): 5-60 min scan

Analysis of Functional MRI

Task FMRI

Tag

Control

Resting-State FMRI & Connectivity

ASL

Brain Physiology: Electrical

Information Transfer:

- large changes in membrane potential leading to action potential
- chemical neurotransmission across synapses

Brain Physiology: Metabolic

Information Transfer:

- large changes in membrane potential leading to action potential
- chemical neurotransmission across synapses

Signalling Energy Use

Magnetic Properties of Haemoglobin

Oxy-haemoglobin

Diamagnetic

(same as tissue)

Deoxy-
haemoglobin

Paramagnetic

$\Delta\chi \approx 0.2$ ppm

Mini MR Physics: T_2^* Effect

B_0 field within voxel	Effect
Large change (inhomogeneity)	Loss of Signal
No change (uniform B_0)	Good Signal

Metal artefact above (obvious)

BOLD effect (subtle version : reduction in signal)

BOLD Effect

BOLD Effect

Increased Neuronal Activity

Magnetic field less perturbed
→ Less dephasing
→ More signal

Images - Low Resolution FMRI

- A sequence of low resolution T_2^* -weighted volumes are taken during the FMRI experiment
- Optimised for BOLD sensitivity and speed
- Take one volume every 1-3 seconds
- Often take around 200 volumes (10 minutes)
- An FMRI volume is shown here in *orthogonal* view

Images - High Resolution MRI

- Need a single, high-resolution T_1 -weighted image for each subject (not each session)
- Used to map activations onto
- Best way to identify anatomy
- Better accuracy for registration of results to standard space

Functional MRI “Limitations”

- Does *not* measure electrical activity
- Does *not* measure metabolic activity
- BOLD-fMRI is qualitative

Functional MRI Artefacts

Hardware-related

Distortion

Signal Loss

Physiological

Physiological Noise

... plus most diffusion artefacts (not eddy currents)
and all structural artefacts

- Distortion due to B_0 inhomogeneity (air in sinuses)
 - acquisition-and-analysis related fixes needed (fieldmap)
- Physiological noise is more problematic near the brainstem
 - acquire physiological measurements & do analysis fix
- Motion can also be a significant problem (some analysis fixes)

Functional MRI “Limitations”

- Does *not* measure electrical activity
- Does *not* measure metabolic activity
- BOLD-fMRI is qualitative
- Need good T_2^* sensitivity
 - causes lost signal in inferior regions
- Sensitive to fast imaging artefacts
- ASL suffers from worse SNR

Functional MRI: Acquisition

Basic tips for acquisition

- Use optimised sequences/protocol for your scanner/site
- Get *fieldmap* (B_0) for compensating distortion/signal-loss
 - blip-up-blip-down is not an option for functional MRI
- For inferior-frontal/temporal areas apply acquisition techniques to minimise signal loss
 - e.g. *thin slices, slice angulation, z-shims, parallel imaging, ...*
- Isotropic voxels (or close) are better for analysis generally
- Do not do upsampling on scanner (sometimes the default)
- For *small FOV* also take one single whole-brain EPI
- Biggest interaction of exp. design-acquisition-analysis so think carefully about all parts **before** acquiring data!

Complementary techniques

Complementary techniques

Physiological Measures

Complementary techniques

Structural MRI:

- CT (bones/membranes/vessels/tumours)
- Histology (microstructure)

Diffusion MRI:

- Tracer studies (individual fibres)
- Histology (myelin/axon dimensions/glia)

Functional MRI:

- PET/SPECT (metabolic/ligands/low res.)
- EEG/MEG (electrical activity/high temporal res.)
- NIRS (haemodynamics/high temporal res.)
- TMS/TDCS (alter regional brain function)
- Electrodes (single cells/cell groups)

Complementary Methods:

FreeSurfer

Cortical modelling and flattening
Surface-based registration

Subcortical segmentation

- Model G-W surface, inflate sulci, then expand each cortical hemisphere to a spherical surface
- Align across subjects on the cortical surface
- Display activation on inflated/flattened surface
- Cortical thickness measurements
- Multi-subject fMRI stats on standard spherical surface (reduces subject variability)
- Subcortical segmentation
- Easy to pass data between FSL & FreeSurfer

... and now for the
first practical ...

